

Pelargonium sidoides Black Pelargonium

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 25 - 30 cm in height

Distribution:

The black pelargonium has a wide distribution. It occurs throughout the eastern Cape, Lesotho, Free State and southern and south-western Gauteng in South Africa. It usually grows in short grassland and sometimes with occasional shrubs and trees on stony soil varying from sand to clay-loam, shale or basalt.

Importance:

It is a well-known medicinal plant and is used by the pharmaceutical industry for the treatment of bronchitis. It is also utilized for a variety of folk-medicinal purposes, including the treatment of sore throats and congestion. Its tubers are harvested in the wild and exported for the international herbal medicine trade.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 40.55 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.93 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.45 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 5.4%, Duplicated: 94.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 12 895.83 kilobases

Contig number: 1 320

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Renée Prins

CenGen (Pty) Ltd

cengen@cengen.co.za